

Determination of Methanol using J-Acid

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A sensitive method for spectrophotometric determination of methanol in environmental samples is described. Methanol is oxidised to formaldehyde with acidic potassium permanganate and the resulting formaldehyde is reacted with J-acid to form a yellow dye with green fluorescence having λ_{\max} at 470 nm. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of methanol in effluents from distilleries and polluted air.

Methanol is widely used in many organic industries. Effluents from distilleries and other industries contain considerable quantity of methanol. Ingestion and inhalation of large amounts of methanol causes health hazard¹. The reported threshold limit value² for methanol in air is 200 ppm. Of the various methods reported for methanol only a few are direct and most of them are non-specific^{3,4}. The other reported methods are based upon oxidation of methanol to formaldehyde which is subsequently determined using a variety of methods reported for formaldehyde⁴⁻⁶.

In the present communication, a new reagent is described for indirect spectrophotometric determination of methanol. The methanol is oxidised with acidic potassium permanganate⁷ and the formaldehyde formed is determined with J-acid, which has been earlier used as a sensitive reagent for the determination of trace amounts of formaldehyde⁸. The yellow dye formed with green fluorescence in acidic medium exhibits maximum absorption at 470 nm.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of the yellow dye shows maximum absorption at 470 nm. The reagent blank shows no absorption at this wavelength.

Effect of varying reaction conditions: 2 ml of aliquot of oxidising solution for oxidation of methanol was found optimum. The use of 4-5 drops of 10% Na₂SO₃ was found satisfactory, since dilute solution of sodium sulphite makes the system too aqueous for J-acid and its excess use makes the solution turbid. Time of 10 min for oxidation and 5 min for coupling were found necessary.

Beer's law, sensitivity and reproducibility: Beer's law was followed over a concentration range of 5-70 μg of methanol in 10 ml of final solution. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.2-10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (± 100) and $0.0026 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. Reproducibility of the method was checked by analysing 30 μg of methanol in 10 ml for a period of 7 days. Standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be 0.0045 and $\pm 1.3\%$ respectively for 10 determinations.

Effect of other chemical species: Effect of various diverse species normally associated with methanol was studied by adding known amounts of the species to the aliquots prior to oxidation and measuring absorbance after developing colour with J-acid. Tolerance limit (μg in parenthesis) of various pollutants are as follows in 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ methanol: Hg^{II} Cd^{II} (20); Zn^{II} (30); Ca^{II}, Mg, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} and *m*-dinitrobenzene (100); aniline (300); sulphide, acetic and formic acids (500); phenol (800); sulphate (850); urea (1000); propanol (2000); glucose (4000); ethanol (5000). Most of the organic solvents did not interfere in this method. Formaldehyde and other organic compounds, oxidisable to aldehydes, gave positive interferences. Total time required for an analysis was less than 15 min.

Applications: The method has been successfully applied for determination of methanol in polluted air and in distillery effluent.

As laboratory air does not contain methanol, the samples were obtained by evaporating methanol over a steam-bath in laboratory and then the contaminated air was passed through the absorbing solution taken in an impinger attached to the air-sampling train. After sampling, an aliquot of the solution was taken and analysed (Table 1).

Samples were collected from a nearby distillery and were filtered. An aliquot of the filtrate was diluted with distilled water (1:3) and analysed (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF METHANOL IN DISTILLERY EFFLUENT AND POLLUTED AIR*

Sample	Methanol added (μg)	Methanol found (μg)	
		Present method	Chromotropic method**
Distillery effluent	—	18.6	18.2
	—	12.0	11.8
	—	16.10	15.95
	—	17.15	16.28
Air	10	9.65	9.58
	20	19.46	19.30
	30	28.85	28.55
	50	48.68	48.43

*Mean of three replicate analyses.

**Ref. 11.

The proposed method has been compared with other reported methods and found that it is more sensitive and selective for methanol determination in industrial effluents and other environmental samples (Table 2).

TABLE 2 - COMPARISON WITH OTHER METHODS

Method	λ_{\max} nm	Medium	Formaldehyde* ppm	Methanol* ppm
Schryvers ^a	520	4 M HCl	1.0 ^b	75
ODH ^b	620	Acetate buffer	0.60 ^c	60
Chromotropic acid ^d	578	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	1.0 ^e	4
<i>p</i> -Aminoazo- benzene ^f	505	HCl	0.008 ^g	4
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline ^h	395	HCl	0.2 ⁱ	2
Present method ^j	470	H ₂ SO ₄	0.15 ^k	0.5

*Lower limit of determination. ^aRef. 12. ^bRef. 13.
^cRef. 10. ^dRef. 11. ^eRef. 6. ^fRef. 7. ^gRef. 14. ^hRef. 16.
ⁱRef. 15. ^jPresent method. ^kRef. 8.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Carl-Zeiss Spokol spectrophotometer.

An aqueous solution (1 g dm⁻³) of methanol was prepared from methanol (G.R., S.M.) and a working standard of 10 μ g ml⁻¹ was prepared by appropriate dilution. A 0.4% of 6-amino-1-naphthol-3-sulphonic acid (J-acid, Wilson) was prepared in concentrated H₂SO₄. KMnO₄ (4 g) was dissolved in distilled water (20 ml) to which concentrated H₃PO₄ (15 ml) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (1 ml) were added and the final volume was made up to 100 ml with demineralised water. A 10% aqueous solution of sodium sulphite was used. All reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

Procedure :

Water samples : To an aliquot of water sample containing 5–70 μ g of methanol, was added the oxidising solution (2 ml) and it was allowed to stand in an ice-bath for 10 min. Excess permanganate was then removed with sodium sulphite (5–10 drops). Then J-acid (1 ml) was added to it and heated on a boiling water-bath for 5 min for coupling. It was cooled the volume made up to 10 ml with concentrated H₂SO₄ and the absorbance of yellow dye with green fluorescence was measured at 470 nm against distilled water.

Air samples : A modified Wilson's procedure was used for absorption of methanol from air samples^{9,10}. A known amount of methanol was added to a preheated chamber at 70° and the methanol vapour was absorbed in acidified KMnO₄ solution (5 ml) contained in two impingers connected in series to an air-sampling train fitted with a rotameter and vacuum pump. Air was drawn through the impingers for 15 min at a rate of 0.5 dm³ min⁻¹. After sampling, the solutions were allowed to stand for 10 min in an ice-bath for oxidation. Finally an aliquot was taken, decolorised and analysed as recommended above.

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